

SPONDYLODISKITIS: MODERN APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS

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Resume; restart. At the same time, the diagnosis of spondylodiscitis is difficult and often occurs with a significant delay after the appearance of the first symptoms, which is due to the rarity of the disease, the non-specificity of its manifestations, and therefore the lack of disease awareness of doctors on issues of infectious lesions of the spine. The current problem with determining the etiology of the disease leads to irrational antibiotic therapy, long-term treatment and increased costs. Surgical treatment of spondylodiscitis is delayed due to the lack of strict guidelines. Key words: spondylodiscitis, infection, diagnosis, biopsy, treatment, surgery.

Diagnostics

Clinical presentation of DM Clinical symptoms of DM are not specific. The onset of the disease, as a rule, is ignored, and the alarm signal is constant back pain, which increases at night, when walking, and general intoxication symptoms increase. This condition can last in different ways: from 10 days to a month, depending on the severity of the process. The most common symptom of diabetes is back pain, but up to 15% of patients may not experience back pain. Pain syndrome depends on the localization and degree of the pathological process in the spine. The most common localization of pain and, accordingly, injuries are in the lumbar region, less often in the chest region, and very rarely in the cervical region. Pain in the thoracic spine can be similar to pneumonia or pleurisy, in the lower thoracic and lumbar spine it mimics acute abdomen, dynamic obstruction, paranephritis and osteochondrosis. This leads to incorrect diagnosis or even unnecessary surgery. Fever is a less common symptom, occurring in half of patients. Fever rarely occurs in diabetes with tuberculosis etiology. The spread of the infectious process to the spinal canal is accompanied by the development of radicular syndrome with limitation of motor activity, signs of irritation or fading of reflexes, and sensory disturbances in the areas of the affected roots. As the disease progresses, symptoms of spinal cord compression appear with a frequency of 10 to 64%: plegia with the development of paresis of the limbs, increased neurological deficit, pelvic dysfunction with delayed urination and defecation. Spinal deformities in the form of kyphosis are common with tuberculosis. Cervical DM may present with dysphagia or torticollis. Acute pain during palpation of vertebral tumors of the spine and paravertebral region at the level of the lesion is the most common symptom

detected during examination of the patient (in 78-97% of cases), which is often associated with a limited range. movement and spasm of paravertebral muscles . The lack of characteristic symptoms of the disease leads to late diagnosis and poor treatment results. On average, the period between the onset of the disease and the diagnosis lasts from 8 weeks to 3 months.

Laboratory diagnostics

a sensitive but non-specific indicator of infection. In many studies, this indicator increases in more than 90% of cases, its average value is from 43 to 87 mm per hour. A decrease in ESR of 25% or more is a good prognostic sign of therapy. C-reactive protein is elevated in more than 90% of patients with diabetes. A rapid decrease in the level of C-reactive protein indicates the correct choice of therapy and allows injectable forms of antibiotics to be administered orally. Leukocytosis is detected only in 30-50% of patients and is the least sensitive inflammatory sign of the disease.

Microbiological diagnosis

It is very important to determine the etiological factor that caused the infectious process in the diagnosis of diabetes. This is due to the wide range of possible pathogens and the increase in resistance to antibiotics. Empirically prescribed antibiotic therapy often leads to the development of complications, expansion of indications for surgical treatment, as well as prolongation of the patient's stay in the hospital and increased costs of treatment. The simplest method of microbiological research is blood culture . However, this method has diagnostic value only in 25-33% of cases and is positive only in cases of infection due to a highly virulent strain. In this case, blood should be taken for culture at the height of the fever and before the start of antibacterial therapy, which is rarely possible. It is recommended to carry out three cultures with the determination of sensitivity to antibiotics. Early detection of the tuberculosis process in the spine allows identifying patients with diabetes of tuberculosis etiology, which reduces the spread of infection, and also allows early initiation of anti-tuberculosis therapy in a specialized hospital. Exclusion of diabetes caused by mycobacteria tuberculosis , use several methods. Diaskintest is a test that determines whether a patient has tuberculosis. The Mantoux test is less important today, because it only detects the active process of tuberculosis, and also gives a high frequency of false results. These methods are the simplest and cheapest. Pathogenic DNA detection methods: LPA (Hain test), GenExpert . These methods are the fastest and most accurate for diagnosing tuberculosis. Their important advantage is the possibility of simultaneous detection of drug

resistance of mycobacteria. Biopsy of the pathological focus Biopsy of the infected area followed by microbiological examination in different studies ranges from 19% to 100%. This technique is often used in patients with negative blood cultures. Biopsies in these patients are positive in 43-78% of cases. Biopsy material should be grown in a medium diagnostic for aerobic, anaerobic microorganisms, fungi and mycobacteria. At the same time, the biopsy material should be subjected to histological examination. Its main role is to distinguish purulent and granulomatous processes. Biopsy material can also be tested using PCR. This is a very effective method that allows you to detect microorganisms in minimal quantities even after the start of antibiotic therapy. Currently, the methods of identifying the DNA of microorganisms are developing rapidly. However, the main problem with their use is their high cost. There are closed (percutaneous) and open methods of biopsy . Among the closed methods for obtaining material for infectious diseases of the spinal cord, the most suitable is a puncture biopsy, the varieties of which are fine needle aspiration biopsy and trephine biopsy. A puncture biopsy is performed under ultrasound kovy , fluoroscopic , CT or MRI control. Ultrasound examination is ineffective in diagnosing diseases of the spinal cord. Its capabilities are limited to the detection of superficial lesions of the cervical spine. Biopsy under fluoroscopic control is the simplest, cheapest, short-term method that allows monitoring the process in real time. The disadvantage of this method is its inability to image the surrounding soft tissues. Computed tomography visualization of the procedure is standard in many developed countries. CT control allows you to plan the trajectory of the needle, avoid lung damage, and access hard-to-reach areas. Disadvantages include the duration of the procedure and the effect of ionizing radiation. The advantage of CT control over fluoroscopy is the ability to see soft tissues as well as bone, as well as more accurate visualization of the needle, especially for small pathological lesions. MRI control is used only in large specialized neurosurgery centers. Its advantages include strong contrast between soft and bony tissues, absence of ionizing radiation , and multidimensional imaging capabilities. An open biopsy is performed during surgery. For the spine, if the area of pathological formation is removed for research purposes, cross-sectional biopsy is more important. An open biopsy is diagnostic in about 80% of cases.

Instrumental diagnostics

subchondral sclerosis, loss of definition of the vertebral endplates, and decreased intervertebral disc height. Late changes include destruction of the

opposite end plate and a decrease in vertebral height. However, 2-8 weeks after the onset of symptoms, symptoms do not begin to develop, and false positive results can lead to the development of degenerative changes in the spine. Different isotopes are used for radionuclide diagnosis of diabetes. Technetium-99m has high sensitivity - up to 90%, but less specificity - 78%. Gallium-67 is used in combination with radiography, and the sensitivity of this method reaches 90%, specificity - 100%, and accuracy - 94%. CT is one of the best ways to diagnose bone lesions. CT can detect changes such as early destruction of the endplate (before it can be seen on radiography), later sequestration, and pathological calcification found in tuberculosis. Changes in the intervertebral disc appear as hypodense areas. MRI is the method of choice in the instrumental diagnosis of diabetes. It has a sensitivity of approximately 96%, a specificity of 93%, and an accuracy of 94%. Its advantage over other methods is the high ability to visualize the epidural space and the spinal cord. Characteristic changes include decreased signal intensity from the intervertebral disc and adjacent vertebral bodies on T1, increased signal on T2, and loss of endplate definition on T1. Gadolinium contrast increases the accuracy of the study (especially in early diagnosis, there may be no other changes), and also helps distinguish infectious lesions from degenerative changes and neoplasms. With tuberculosis lesions of the spinal cord, there are usually no changes in the intervertebral disc, but paravertebral abscesses, changes in the back structures of the vertebrae can be detected, and long vertebrae are also involved in the process and their destruction is detected. In the presence of purulent diabetes, MRI changes during treatment often indicate a lack of dynamics or even a worsening of the process. This leads to unnecessary surgical interventions. Positive dynamics of MRI Pictures may be absent during the first 4-8 weeks of therapy. Accordingly, it is not recommended to rely on MRI data to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment

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